

Merocyanines Derived from Substituted 4-Hydroxycoumarins. Part I

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Several merocyanines, derived from substituted 4-hydroxycoumarins as acidic nuclei and several basic nuclei, have been prepared. Arguments have been put forward to explain why the absorption peak of the symmetrical cyanine series, derived from benzothiazole, lies between the analogous series of the dyes derived from benzoxazole and quinaldine.

The present investigation describes a number of merocyanines derived from four different 4-hydroxycoumarins, *i.e.* those derived from phenol, α - and β -naphthols, and resorcinol, used as the acidic nuclei, and a number of basic nuclei. In course of our studies on the influence of structural changes on absorption, it was considered worth while to evaluate the effect of substituents in the aromatic rings of 4-hydroxycoumarins on the absorption of merocyanine dyes derived from them. 4-Hydroxycoumarins, which have the structure shown below, possess an active ketomethylene group which can be utilised in the preparation of merocyanines etc.

Table I records the absorption maxima of merocarbo-, merodicarbo-, and merotri-carboeyanines derived from the above 4-hydroxycoumarins and some basic nuclei.

Incidentally, the absorption maxima of the dyes derived from quinaldine have been noticed to be higher than those derived from benzothiazole, which in turn show higher absorption maxima than the dyes derived from benzoxazole. It is well known that in the symmetrical cyanine series, the absorption peak of the dyes derived from benzothiazole lies between the analogous series of the dyes derived from benzoxazole and quinaldine. In the case of merocyanines studied by us, this can be explained as follows.

As is well known, the sulphur atom functions as the resonance transmitter in the same way as a vinylene group. The structure, such as (Ib), will contribute to resonance hybrid since it represents an effective increase in the length of the conjugated path. In the case of benzothiazole, similar contributions are also possible as sulphur functions as a resonance transmitter. This is, however, ruled out in the case of benzoxazole as the structure of type (III b) is not possible.

(I)

Merocyanine from 4-hydroxycoumarin and quinoline-2

(Ia)

Dipolar structure

(Ib)

(II)

Merocyanine from 4-hydroxycoumarin and benzothiazole

(IIa)

Dipolar structure

(IIa)

(IIb)

(III)

Mercyanine from 4-hydroxycoumarin and benzoxazole

(IIIa)

Dipolar structure

(IIIb)

(Not possible)

4-Hydroxycoumarins were prepared by the reaction of appropriate phenol with malonic acid in presence of phosphorus oxychloride and anhydrous zinc chloride by the method of Shah *et al.*¹

The merocyanines ($n=1,2,3$) were prepared by condensing 2-(2-acetanilidovinyl), 2-(4-acetanilido-1,3-butadienyl), and 2-(6-acetanilido-1,3,5-hexatrienyl) derivatives of the quaternary salt with the desired 4-hydroxycoumarin in anhydrous ethanol in presence of triethylamine.

EXPERIMENTAL

3 - [(2 - Acetanilidovinylbenzothiazolin - 2 ylidene) - ethylidene] - 7 - hydroxychroman - 2,4 - dione. — 2-(2-Acetanilidovinyl)benzothiazole methiodide was prepared by the method already reported².

2-Acetanilidovinylbenzothiazole methiodide (4.3 g.) and 4,7-dihydroxycoumarin (1.8 g.) were refluxed in ethanol and triethylamine for 2 min. The product separating on cooling was filtered, washed with dilute ethanol, and finally recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. $> 310^{\circ}$, yield 54%. (Found: C, 64.32; H, 3.46. $C_{19}H_{13}O_4NS$ requires C, 64.05; H, 3.70%).

3 - [4-(3-Methylbenzothiazolin - 2 - ylidene) buten - 1 - ylidene] - 7 - hydroxychroman - 2,4 - dione. — 2-(4-Acetanilido-1,3-butadienyl)benzothiazole methiodide was prepared by the method already reported².

2-(4-Acetanilido-1,3-butadienyl)benzothiazole methiodide(4.6 g.) and 4,7-dihydroxycoumarin (1.8 g.) were refluxed in ethanol and triethylamine for a minutes. On cooling, a solid separated. It was filtered, washed with ethanol, and finally crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 252° , yield 51%. (Found: C, 65.32; H, 3.81. $C_{21}H_{15}O_4NS$ requires C, 66.81; H, 3.97%).

3-[6-(3-Methylbenzothiazolin-2-ylidene)hexa-2,4-dien-1-ylidene]-7-hydroxychroman-2,4-dione. — 2-(6-Acetanilido-1,3,5-hexatrienyl)benzothiazole methiodide was prepared according to the method already reported.²

2-(6-Acetanilido-1,3,5-hexatrienyl)benzothiazole methiodide(4.8 g.) and 4,7-dihydroxycoumarin (1.9 g.) were refluxed in ethanol and triethylamine for a minute. The solid separating on cooling was filtered, washed with ethanol, and finally crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 158° , yield 49%. (Found: C, 68.08; H, 4.09. $C_{23}H_{17}O_4NS$ requires C, 68.48; H, 4.21%)

The analytical data of other merocyanine dyes, prepared as described above, are recorded in Table II.

1. *J. Org. Chem.*, 1980, 25, 677.

2. Rout *et al.*, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1961, 20B, 121.

TABLE I

Nature of nucleus A.	Absorption maxima (m μ).			Absorption maxima (m μ).		
	n = 1.	n = 2.	n = 3.	n = 1.	n = 2.	n = 3.
	B = Chroman-2,4-dione.			B = 7-Hydroxychroman-2,4-dione.		
Benzothiazole	400	584	670	490	590	680
Benzoxazole	465	550	627	452	546	624
Quinoline-2	508	592	..	507	597	..
	B = 5,6-Benzochroman-2,4-dione.			B = 7,8-Benzochroman-2,4-dione.		
Benzothiazole	495	600	687	502	600	684
Benzoxazole	468	556	646	465	554	645
Quinoline-2	509	602	..	512	598	..

••TABLE II

Nucleus A.	M.P.	Yield.	λ_{max} .	Found.	Reqd.	M.P.	Yield.	λ_{max} .	Found.	Reqd.
Dimethin merocyanines (n=1).										
	Nucleus B = Chroman-2,4-dione.					Nucleus B = 7-Hydroxychroman-2,4-dione.				
Benzothiazole	*254°	55%	490m μ	C : 67.48 H : 3.61	68.06 3.86	> 310°	54%	490m μ	C : 64.32 H : 3.46	64.95 3.70
Benzoxazole	173°	40	465	C : 70.68 H : 3.84	71.47 4.07	> 300°	49	452	C : 66.93 H : 3.74	68.06 3.88
4-Phenylthiazole	149°	63	505	C : 69.34 H : 4.02	69.60 4.15	208°	71	475	C : 65.80 H : 3.79	66.84 3.97
Quinoline-2	226°	41	508	C : 76.01 H : 4.43	76.59 4.56	203°	68	501	C : 71.89 H : 4.20	73.04 4.35
Tetramethin merocyanines (n=2).										
Benzothiazole	239°	67	584	C : 68.93 H : 3.96	69.51 4.09	252°	51	580	C : 65.32 H : 3.81	66.81 3.97
Benzoxazole	144°	55	550	H : 72.30 H : 4.19	72.85 4.34	*235°	60	540	C : 68.67 H : 3.98	69.51 4.14
4-Phenylthiazole	108°	58	583	C : 70.82 H : 4.26	71.26 4.38	*190°	46	556	C : 67.45 H : 3.99	68.30 4.22
Quinoline-2	95°	43	592	C : 77.06 H : 4.66	77.40 4.78	*271°	39	597	C : 73.65 H : 4.62	74.21 4.68
Hexamethin merocyanines (n=3).										
Benzothiazole	*167°	64	670	C : 69.91 H : 4.08	70.36 4.27	167°	45	624	C : 68.81 H : 4.07	70.36 4.27
Benzoxazole	154°	68	627	C : 72.95 H : 4.31	73.50 4.47	158°	49	680	C : 68.08 H : 4.09	68.48 4.21

*With decomposition.

**Vide structure in Table I.

TABLE II (contd.)

Nucleus A.	M.P.	Yield.	$\lambda_{\max}$.	Found.		Reqd.		$\lambda_{\max}$.	Found.	Reqd.
				C	H	C	H			
Dimethin merocyanines (n=1).										
Nucleus B=5,6-Benzochroman-2,4-dione.						Nucleus B=7,8-Benzochroman-2,4-dione.				
Benzothiazole	126°	62%	405m	C : 70.45 H : 3.63	71.68 3.89	180°	61%	502m μ	C : 70.19 H : 3.62	71.68 3.89
Benzoxazole	*276°	60	468	C : 73.96 H : 3.88	74.79 4.06	*253°	66	465	C : 73.54 H : 3.93	74.79 4.06
4-Phenylthiazole	212°	44	485	C : 71.84 H : 3.98	72.90 4.13	92°	54	478	C : 71.68 H : 3.97	72.99 4.13
Quinoline-2	*200°	38	509	C : 78.10 H : 4.21	79.15 4.49	213°	59	512	C : 77.85 H : 4.32	79.15 4.49
Tetramethin merocyanines (n=2).										
Benzothiazole	204°	56	600	C : 71.66 H : 3.89	72.90 4.12	182°	57	600	C : 71.67 H : 3.92	72.99 4.12
Benzoxazole	265°	51	556	C : 74.81 H : 4.03	75.77 4.29	> 300°	40	554	C : 74.63 H : 4.07	75.77 4.29
4-Phenylthiazole	> 300°	63	550	C : 73.05 H : 4.11	74.13 4.34	295°	43	554	C : 73.32 H : 4.14	74.13 4.34
Quinoline-2	258°	60	602	C : 78.95 H : 4.62	80.55 4.74	*242°	67	598	C : 78.81 H : 4.58	80.55 4.74
Hexamethin merocyanines (n=3).										
Benzothiazole	185°	37	687	C : 71.96 H : 4.01	73.32 4.23	190°	54	684	C : 72.14 H : 4.09	73.32 4.23
Benzoxazole	237°	45	646	C : 75.16 H : 4.18	76.29 4.40	*258°	51	645	C : 75.11 H : 4.23	76.29 4.40

*With decomposition,

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